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REVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF STRATEGIC PLANNING ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN RWANDA

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ABSTRACT:

The study was undertaken on reviewing of impact of the strategic planning on performance of planning firms in Kigali Special Economic Zone in Gasabo District. The descriptive design was used because it ensured complete description of the situation. The target population of interest in this study comprised of 199 organizations in Kigali Special Economic Zone in 2020 Gasabo District involving in strategic planning of their businesses. The sample size for the study was selected from the organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone in Gasabo District. The study targeted a sample size of 60 firms. The study adopted non-probability purposive sampling method to arrive at the participating organizational performance. The study performed data collected through a questionnaire structured to meet the objectives of the study. Descriptive statistics was undertaken to analyze quantitative qualitative data using content analysis. The findings strongly acknowledged that strategic planning is the foundation that improves the business processes and ultimately reduces the internal costs of operation. The study concluded that there is a definite strategic fit between the needs of the environment and what the business offers, as well as what the business needs vis a viz what the environment can provide. The study also concluded that there is a need for firms to analyze the external environment pertaining what they do. This is great importance for researchers and firms as it helps them comprehend the motivation of firms' activities and helps them to take appropriate action and respond to the changing environment.

INTRODUCTION

Strategic planning is a backbone support to strategic management and it is a major process in the conduct of strategic management (Awino, Mutoria, & Oeba, 2012). Wagner (2013), stated that the importance of strategic planning can be explained from four points of view including environmental scanning, strategy formulation, and linking goals to budgets and strategic planning as a process. The strategy planning process starts with setting organizational goals. The strategic planning process is applied by management to establish objectives, set goals, and schedule activities for achieving those goals and includes a method for measuring progress (Bulle, 2012). According to Pearce and Robinson (2008), the strategic planning process can be showed as a series of steps; strategy formulation (Company Vision and Mission, Company Objectives and Internal analysis), situation analysis and environmental scanning (Competitor, industry, Market analysis and strategy selection), strategy implementation and strategy evaluation and control. Strategic planning is a critical part of the strategic management process, which aids non-governmental organizations formulate and appreciate strategies aimed at greater performance effectiveness, improved accountability measures, and sustainable competitive advantage (Awino, Mutoria, & Oeba, 2012).

Environmental scanning is a management tool that uses external information to improve strategic decision-making Managers that use environmental scanning are able to identify new trends and opportunities (Bischoff, 2012). Performance is the yield or results of activities carried out in relation to the purposes being pursued and to effectively implement the strategic plan, management must know if the plan's goals are being achieved on time and with the allocated resources. Performance can only be managed if it can be accurately measured (Awino & Mutua, 2014). According to Ilesanmi (2011), the problem in most companies is not a lack of measures, but a lack of focused and effective measures. The challenges in selecting the right measures include choosing the right leading and lagging indicators, benchmarking (entails feedback control, identifying gaps and putting strategies in place to fill the gaps) against competitors, balancing financial and non-financial measures, and using an appropriate number of measures (Awino & Mutua, 2014).

Antikainen (2014) alludes to the fact that performance is a key factor with specific reference to the organization capacity for progress in the competition field. The improvement in improvement provides a good opportunity for firms to contribute to the organizations' bottom line through the improvement of the production processes, rather than concentrating on only the reduction or omission of costs (Ramirez & Nembhard, 2014). Organizational performance remains of great concern today to all organizations including private, public, and profit or not for profit. Organizational performance is a recurrent theme of great interest to both scholars and practitioners. Researchers and practitioners alike have attempted to understand why some organizations achieve higher levels of performance than others (Mkalama, 2014).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The existence of diverse planning processes in various businesses should be expected but with little or no resemblance to the planning process found in large organizations. For these reasons, over the past decades, numerous studies have been conducted on the construction of models to aid managers and executives in making better decisions concerning the complex and highly uncertain business environment. In spite of the work that has been conducted in the area of strategic planning we still know little about factors influencing it. Results show that researches on contextual factors influencing strategic planning processes are either limited or have produced contradictory results especially studies relating to decisions on familiarity magnitude of impact, organizational size, firm's performance, dynamism hostility, heterogeneity, industry, cognitive diversity, cognitive conflict, and manager's need for achievement of strategic planning processes (Awino & Mutua, 2014). Several studies have been conducted on strategic planning in organizations in Rwanda, but none has focused on strategic planning, and specifically on the factors, which influence strategic planning processes. Even though studies have been done on strategic planning; none was carried out in planning firms in Kigali Special Economic zone. It is with this in mind that this study sought to fill the gap by trying to identify how strategic planning influences organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The general objective of the study was to review the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance in Rwanda.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- [1] To find out vision, mission and action plan as strategic planning tools lead to performance of organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District
- [2] To evaluate the nature of strategic planning by organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District
- [3] To identify strategic planning practices contributing to organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- [1] Which is the vision, mission and action plan as strategic planning tools lead to performance of organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District?
- [2] Which is the nature of strategic planning by organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District?
- [3] What are the strategic planning practices contributing to organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The review of documented scholarly work is relevant to effects of strategic planning and organization performance. The literature embraced related studies conducted elsewhere and their arguments and findings advanced by other scholars on the issue under scrutiny in this research. Literature on strategy formulation was presented first, followed by the influence of strategic planning on organizational performance.

Vision, Mission and Action Plan as Strategic Planning Tools

Mullane (2002) argued that mission and vision statements are useful for practical day-to-day operations, taking a contrary view to those who assert they are archaic documents that are typically exhibited as wall hangings. Several works (Mullane 2002) have outlined how vision statements can be used to build a common and shared sense of purpose and also serve to as conduit through which employees' focus are shaped. Vision statements motivate, shape behaviors, cultivate high levels of commitment and ultimately influence positively on employee performance. Vision statements are widely believed to be antecedents to any strategy formulation effort (Mullane, 2002). Majetka et al. (2013), advised that mission statements could induce desirable behaviours if it is first clearly communicated and reinforced through the reward system. According to Hugh and Michael (2002), the one or two sentences vision statements most companies make available to the company provide only a glimpse of what executives are really thinking and the strategic course they have chartered. Company personnel really have much better understanding where the company is headed and why is revealed in the in the official vision. But the real purpose of strategic vision is to serve as management for giving the organization a sense of direction. Vision statements should to be ambitious and challenging yet attainable enough to evoke employee's ingenuity and creativity as far as its realization is concerned. Core values

are enduring principles, ideologies and worldviews that the founding fathers of organization hold in high esteem; these are sometimes referred to organizational vision (Sufi and Lyons, 2003).

Nature of Strategic Planning

Behn (2013) posited that performance measures serve different purposes in an organization. He observed that performance allows managers to evaluate, control, budget, motivate, promote, celebrate, learn and improve different aspects in an organization. Therefore, no single measure is appropriate for all the eight purposes of organizational learning (Srimai, Damsaman and Bangchokdee, 2011). Evaluation of performance has significant importance in defining the performance levels and standards within an organization (Chenhall, 2015). A study conducted by Cruz, Scapens and Major (2011) on 54 organizations on the effect of performance evaluations on organizational performance revealed the existence of a significant relations between the two. The study also noted that 74% of the organizations indicated that evaluation of performance was important in that it provided mechanisms for reflection, realignment, and restructuring of their projects to meet organizational performance targets.

Choi et al. (2013), argue that evaluation of performance provides essential feedback to employees and the organization on areas they need to improve. Such knowledge is not only essential but fundamental in establishing performance cultures within organization. Aremu (2010), posits that strategy is needed to focus effort and promote coordination of activities. Without strategy an organization becomes bunch of individuals, hence strategy is required to ensure collective actions and concentration of efforts towards achieving organizational plans and objective. There are a wide diversity of viewpoints, approaches and models that are applied in strategic planning. The way that a strategic plan is developed depends on the nature of the organization's leadership, culture of the organization, complexity of the organization's environment, size of the organization, expertise of planners. For example, there are a variety of strategic planning models, including goals- based, issues-based, organic, scenario. Goals based planning is probably the most common and starts with focus on the organization's mission (and vision and/or values), goals to work toward the mission, strategies to achieve the goals, and action planning. Issues-based strategic planning often starts by examining issues facing the organization, strategies to address those issues, and action plans.

Effective Strategic Management Approaches

Strategic intent represents a crystallized vision of an organization's aspired direction of growth and plays an essential role in shaping organizational resource allocation and capability development (Hamel & Prahalad 2009). Firms with low levels of strategic intent have a scarcity of ambition and frequently have trouble with effective goal setting. Strategic intent is about defeating competition and winning the market. It symbolizes and expresses a process of achieving competitive advantage (Brand, 2003). This is because for an organization to win it should have certain capability that others do not have or cannot easily and promptly imitate. To realize strategic intent, some level of activities (strategic action) and behaviour is required. Such activities comprise management focusing the attention of the organization on the essence of winning, motivating people by communicating the value of the target, leaving room for individual and team contribution, sustaining enthusiasm by providing new operational definition as circumstances changes and using intent consistently to guide resources allocation (Hamel & Prahalad, 2009). Strategic planning consists of planning processes that are undertaken in firms to develop strategies that might contribute to performance (Tapinos et al., 2005).

The main aspects of strategic planning are long-time in nature. The formalities employed, use of planning instruments, and frequent control of plans are a major component is strategic planning process. Strategic planning contributes to the firm's performance by generating relevant information, by providing a better understanding of the importance of the environment, and by reducing uncertainty (Hodgetts and Kuratko, 2001). Cruz et al. (2011), noted that standards are set not only for the final output but also for intermediate stages of output. Once these standards have been established, evaluation determines whether the goals were met or not. Evaluation makes it possible to compare and measure the actual performance of predetermined times.

Strategic Planning practices and Organizational Performance

Over time the concept and practice of strategic planning practices has been embraced worldwide and across private and public sectors because of its perceived contribution to organizational effectiveness and to fast-track performance. Strategic planning is arguably significant ingredient in the conduct of strategic management. Porter (1985), noted that despite the criticism levelled against strategic planning during the 1970s and 80s it was still useful, and it only needed to be improved and recanted. Greenly (2011) noted that strategic planning has potential advantages and intrinsic values that eventually translate into improved firm performance. It is therefore a vehicle that facilitates improved firm performance. Strategic planning can be viewed from content or a process viewpoint. The content involves the different elements of the strategic plan which vary from firm to firm. Process entails the mechanisms for the creation of the strategic plan and its implementation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research design is the plan and organization of investigation to discover answers to research questions. According to Burns and Grove (2003), descriptive design portrays an accurate profile of persons, events, or account of the characteristics, for example behavior, opinions, abilities, beliefs, and knowledge of a particular individual, situation or group. The descriptive design is preferred because it ensured complete description of strategies, making sure that there is minimum bias in the collection of data. The target population of interest in this study comprised of organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District. The number of registered organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District is 199 (RDB, 2020). In this study, the sample frame comprised the 199 registered organizational in Kigali Special Economic Zone in Gasabo District. The sample size of 60 respondents for the study was selected from the organizational in Kigali Special Economic Zone in Gasabo District

Table 1: Sample Size

Year of operation	Population	Sample (30%)
Below 5 years	46	14
5 – 7 years	39	12
8 – 10 years	114	34
Total	199	60

The study performed data collected through a questionnaire structured to meet the objectives of the study. Part A of the questionnaire covered the demographics of the respondent which enabled the researcher to collect standardized data that will produce results that will be easily compared and understood. Part B covered Vision, Mission and Action Plan in Strategic Planning, part C was based on Strategic Planning practices by firms, part D covered the influence of Strategic Planning Practices on Firm’s Performance and Part E was on the Firm’s Performance. The respondents were asked to rate extent to which the parameters influence performance on their business on a Likert scale of 1 to 5. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents by the researcher within a specified period of time. The raw data was examined, checked and cleaned for completeness and comprehensibility by eliminating unusable data, interpreting ambiguous answers and eliminating contradictory data from related questions. The data was then coded and entered into statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) program and descriptive analysis ran and data analyzed and cleaned. Descriptive statistics was used in the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data using content analysis. The data were in qualitative and quantitative in nature and data presentation was done by the use of tables and figures. The following linear model was used:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \epsilon$$

Where Y is the firm’s performance, β_0 is constant and ϵ is the error term of the model.

X1 = Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning

X2 = Strategic planning practices by firms

X3 = Influence of strategic planning practices on firm’s performance

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The respondents comprised of employees from surveyed organizational performance in Kigali Special Economic Zone, Gasabo District. Out of the 60 issued questionnaires, 56 questionnaires representing 93% of the total questionnaires distributed were returned fully completed. The response of 93% facilitated towards gathering sufficient data that was generalized to reflect the perceptions, attitudes, behaviors or values of respondents. In order to establish the relationship between the dependent and independent variables, the study conducted a multiple regression analysis. The results of regression analysis were presented by the use of regression model summary, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and beta coefficient tables. Regression analysis can only be performed once the assumptions of normality, linearity, independence, and multicollinearity are not violated. Several tests were conducted as shown in the following subsections. A normality test was conducted to determine whether the sample data follows a normal distribution. A normal probability plot was constructed and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test conducted. The Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual shows a plot of expected normal value against the actual (observed) normal value. A normally distributed data will be shown when actual values line up along the diagonal line joining the lower left to the upper right. On the other hand, the K-S test has a null hypothesis that data follows a normal distribution and an alternate hypothesis that data does not follow a normal distribution. Null hypothesis will be rejected if p-value < 0.05. Normality holds if we fail to reject null hypothesis (Motulsky, 2010).

Figure 1 Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Table 2: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

Firm's performance		
N		72
Normal Parameters	Mean	3.2650
	Std. Deviation	.59302
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.074
	Positive	.052
	Negative	-.074
Test Statistic		.074
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200

From table 2, p-value > 0.05 hence we fail to reject null hypothesis and we concluded that the data follows a normal distribution. Furthermore, the normal P-P plot reveals that actual values fit perfectly on the diagonal line confirming the assumption that the data has a normal distribution. The study tested the existence of a linear relationship between the dependent variable (firm's performance) and each of the independent variables. Scatter plots were used in examining these relationships and the results displayed in Figures 2 below. The associated linear equation generated is presented.

Figure 2 Scatterplot

The associated linear equation is given below: $y = 3.2 + 0.48x$

The coefficient of determination 0.576, shows the linear model provides a relatively good fit. Moreover, a straight line in the plot above comfortably fits through the data; hence a linear relationship exists. The study established that the data set does not violate the assumption of linearity and proceeded with linear regression analysis. The study tested the assumption that the residuals were not correlated from one observation to the next. This was critical in helping establish that the size of residuals for one case had no impact on the residuals for the next case. The Durbin-Watson statistics results are displayed in Table 3. The value of the Durbin-Watson statistic ranges from 0 to 4 suggests that the residuals are uncorrelated is the Durbin-Watson statistic is approximately 2. A value close to 0 indicates strong positive correlation, while a value of 4 indicates strong negative correlation. The model summary in Table 3 shows Durbin-Watson statistic = 2.217, which was approximate to 2 and hence the residuals in the data set used in this showed no serial correlation. The data was hence considered adequate for linear regression analysis.

Table 3: Collinearity test with firm’s performance as Dependent Variable

Model	Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF	
1	Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning;	.679	1.473
	Strategic planning practices by firms;	.575	1.739
	Influence of strategic planning practices on firm’s performance;	.555	1.803

Table 3 shows a regression of three independent variables against firm’s performance as the dependent variable. All the VIF values were < 3 and all the tolerance values are ≥ 0.1, meaning the independent variables were not highly correlated firm’s performance and hence the data set did not suffer from multicollinearity. Coefficient of determination explains the extent to which changes in the dependent variable (firm’s performance) can be explained by the change in the independent variables or the percentage of variation in the dependent variable that is explained by all the independent variables. From table 4, the coefficient of determination 0.576 means that 57.6 % of the total variance in independent variables has been explained.

Table 4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.774a	.600	.576	.40074	2.217

Analysis of Variance results reports how well the regression equation fits the data (i.e., predicts the dependent variable) and results are shown in table 5 below.

Table 5. Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.112	4	4.028	25.083	.000b
	Residual	8.211	51	.161		
	Total	24.323	55			

A null hypothesis states that there is no linear relationship between the variables. The F- test can be used to reject the null hypothesis of fail to reject it. $F(4, 55) = 25.083$ and $df = 71$, the test is highly significant ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, and we conclude that there is a linear relationship between the variables in our model and that the regression model is a good fit of the data. Results presented in table 5 reveal that all the independent variables notably; (X1) Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning, (X2) Strategic planning practices by firms, and (X3) Influence of strategic planning practices on firm’s performance. Table 6 presents the results of the test of unstandardized beta coefficients which indicates the equation of the linear model.

Table 6. Beta Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.250	.309		2.091	.037
Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning	.215	.092	.219	2.339	.022

Strategic planning practices by firms	.319	.106	.307	3.010	.004
Influence of strategic planning practices on firm's performance	.248	.090	.288	2.772	.007

a. Dependent Variable: Firm's performance

The prediction equation is $Y = 0.250 + 0.215X_1 + 0.319X_2 + 0.248X_4 + \varepsilon$

Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning, Strategic planning practices by firms and Influence of strategic planning practices on firm's performance have p-value of 0.022, 0.004, and 0.007 respectively. These p-values are statistically significant at 5% significant level. In addition, t-test for these independent variables confirm that they are statistically significant if t-values are greater than 2. As presented in table 6, all the coefficients are found to be positive suggesting that an increase of a unit of Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning, Strategic planning practices by firms or Influence of strategic planning practices leads to an increase in firm's performance. The higher the coefficient values of beta, the more influential the independent variable. As evident from the study, Strategic planning practices by firms has the most influence on firm's performance and Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning has the least influence.

The findings of the study revealed that three of the independent variables notably (X1) Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning, (X2) Strategic planning practices by firms, and (X3) Influence of strategic planning practices on firm's performance have a significance influence on firm's performance. Since the P value < 0.05 level of significance, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that these independent variables significantly influence firm's performance. Regression analysis reveals Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning coefficient of 0.215 and p-value of 0.022 was found to be significant at 5% significant level and this indicates that Vision, mission and action plan in strategic planning has a positive influence on firm's performance, Strategic planning practices by firms coefficient of 319 and p-value of 0.004 was found to be significant at 5% significant level and this indicates that Strategic planning practices by firms has a positive influence on firm's performance, Influence of strategic planning practices on firm's performance coefficient of 0.248 and p-value of 0.004 was found to be significant at significance level of 5% and this indicates that Influence of strategic planning practices on firm's performance has a positive influence on firm's performance.

Conclusion and Recommendation

By developing a strategic plan that incorporates the mission statement, entrepreneurs are more likely to be successful and stay focused on what is important. The mission statement encourages managers and small business owners alike to consider the nature and scope of the business. The study concluded that there must be a strategic fit between what the environment wants and what the business has to offer, as well as between what the business needs and what the environment can provide. As revealed by the findings, every step in the strategic planning process is important. If the firm's direction is not clear, then employees will not know if they are on the right track. If the business environment has not been critically examined, then firms will not understand its internal competences or business opportunities from where appropriate strategies are crafted to facilitate a fit and success.

Recommendations

The strategic planning should therefore be adopted by business organizations to enhance firm's performance. Through an interpretation of information gathered during the environmental analysis, business owners can determine the direction in which a firm should move. Entrepreneurial businesses are driven by vision and high aspirations. Developing a mission statement will help the small business realize their vision. By developing a strategic plan that incorporates the mission statement, entrepreneurs are more likely to be successful and stay focused on what is important. The mission statement encourages managers and small business owners alike to consider the nature and scope of the business. The study recommends that there must be a strategic fit between what the environment wants and what the business has to offer, as well as between what the business needs and what the environment can provide. Firms should consider every step in the strategic planning process as important. If the firm's direction is not clear, then employees will not know if they are on the right track. If the business environment has not been critically examined, then firms will not understand its internal competences or business opportunities from where appropriate strategies are crafted to facilitate a fit and success. The study further recommends that the process of strategic planning should be given its deserved attention in terms of all the prescribed steps within the existing literature.

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